

MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY ON FERMIONIC QUANTUM STATISTICAL SYSTEM

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Abstract:

A quantum statistical system is considered with a modified grand partition function subjected to an external magnetic field. Specifically, the single particle energy levels are redress to include these external influences, and the grand partition function is derived. The results provide an understanding on how to calculate important properties of the system, such as the magnetization and magnetic susceptibility.

Index terms: Statistical Mechanics, Canonical Ensemble, Magnetic field, Susceptibility, Quantum mechanics.

1. Introduction

Statistical mechanics is about deriving global properties of a huge system by analyzing the interactions between its tiny constituents [1]. Quantum statistical mechanics on the other hand is the study of probability potentials and bulk properties of individual particles, taking into account the superposition of wavefunctions and the differences in the statistical nature of particles with integer and half integer spin [3]. In the extreme limit of small systems with only a few degrees of freedom, both the finite size effect and quantum effects influence the thermodynamics properties of the system dramatically. The traditional thermodynamic theory based on classical systems of macroscopic size does not apply anymore, and the quantum statistical generalization of thermodynamics becomes necessary. The interplay between magnetism and quantum statistical mechanics has been an interesting research topic since 1960s. In recent years, with the developments of quantum dots and other confined systems, the study of the interface between quantum statistical mechanics and magnetism begins to attract more and more attention. Studies of quantum statistical mechanics not only promise important potential applications in quantum dots and other confined systems, but also bring new insights to some fundamental problems of thermodynamics.

The grand canonical ensemble is a statistical ensemble that is used to represent the possible states of a mechanical system that are in thermodynamic equilibrium with a reservoir [7]. This ensemble is specified by a system volume, temperature and chemical potential [4]. When an external magnetic field is introduced in the system, the single particle energy is modified, which affects the thermodynamic property of the system. The grand partition function is a statistical mechanical quantity used to describe the number of

accessible states for a system in thermodynamic equilibrium [5]. In this research we derive the modified grand partition function for such a system and investigate its implication, concentrating on magnetization and magnetic susceptibility.

2. Modified Partition Function

We start by considering, the grand partition function which is give by [2]

$$Z = \sum_{\{n_i\}} e^{-\beta(\varepsilon_i - \mu)} \quad (1)$$

For fermions, the occupation number n_i can take value 0 or 1 due to the Pauli exclusive principle. The energy of fermions in a magnetic field includes the kinetic and spin contributions accounting for the Schrödinger Pauli equation

$$\varepsilon_i = \frac{(p - qA)^2}{2m} - \mu_s \cdot S \cdot B \quad (2)$$

Where $-\mu_s = g\mu_B \cdot s$, where μ_B is the bohr magneton given by $\frac{e\hbar}{2m}$ and $s = \hbar\sigma/2$. In quantum mechanics, the Schrödinger Pauli equation is the formulation of the Schrödinger equation for spin- $\frac{1}{2}$ particles, which takes into account the interaction of the particle spin with an external magnetic field. The influence of the magnetic field on the partition function is through the energy levels ε_i . For each particle type, the Schrödinger Pauli equation accounts for the coupling between the magnetic moment and the magnetic field, modifying the energy levels. For fermions, the interaction with the magnetic field through their spin results in splitting of energy levels (Zeeman effect). Fermions obey the Pauli exclusive principle, meaning each state can be occupied by at most one fermion, that is $n_i = 0, n_i = 1$. The contribution of each fermionic state to the grand partition function is:

$$\sum_{n_i=0,1} e^{-\beta(\varepsilon_i - \mu)} = 1 + e^{-\beta(\varepsilon_i - \mu)} \quad (3)$$

Thus for fermions, the grand partition function is the product over all fermionic states

$$Z = \prod_i (1 + e^{-\beta(\varepsilon_i - \mu)}) = Z = \prod_i \left(1 + e^{-\beta\left(\frac{(p_i - qA)^2}{2m} - \mu_s \cdot s_i \cdot B - \mu\right)} \right) \quad (4)$$

3. Result and Discussion

In a grand canonical ensemble, the thermodynamic properties are described by the grand canonical potential, temperature, volume, and the number of particles [4]. Magnetization which is a measure of the magnetic moment of a system is not considered a thermodynamic quantity in the grand canonical ensemble. We incorporate magnetization into the description of a quantum system by considering it as an external parameter. To

find the magnetization, we need to compute the partial derivative of the grand canonical potential with respect to the magnetic field B . Taking the derivative of Z .

$$\frac{\partial Z}{\partial B} = \beta \sum_i \mu_s s_i e^{-\beta \left(\frac{(p_i - qA)^2}{2m} - \mu_s \cdot s_i \cdot B - \mu \right)} \quad (5)$$

We can reconcile the grand partition function as

$$Z = \prod_i \left(1 + e^{-\beta \left(\frac{(p_i - qA)^2}{2m} - \mu_s \cdot s_i \cdot B - \mu \right)} \right) \quad (6)$$

Relating Z and Ω , The grand potential Ω is given by [5].

$$\Omega = -k_B T \ln Z \quad (7)$$

Therefore

$$\frac{\partial \Omega}{\partial B} = -k_B T \frac{1}{Z} \frac{\partial Z}{\partial B} \quad (8)$$

Simplifying this we

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \Omega}{\partial B} &= -k_B T \frac{1}{Z} \left(k_B T \sum_i \mu_s s_i e^{-\beta \left(\frac{(p_i - qA)^2}{2m} - \mu_s \cdot s_i \cdot B - \mu \right)} \right) \\ &= -\frac{1}{Z} \left(\sum_i \mu_s s_i e^{-\beta \left(\frac{(p_i - qA)^2}{2m} - \mu_s \cdot s_i \cdot B - \mu \right)} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

We recall from Eq. (6) Thus

$$\frac{\partial \Omega}{\partial B} = -\frac{\sum_i \mu_s s_i e^{-\beta \left(\frac{(p_i - qA)^2}{2m} - \mu_s \cdot s_i \cdot B - \mu \right)}}{\prod_i \left(1 + e^{-\beta \left(\frac{(p_i - qA)^2}{2m} - \mu_s \cdot s_i \cdot B - \mu \right)} \right)} \quad (10)$$

The numerator is the average value of the magnetic moment

$$\langle M \rangle = -\frac{\sum_i \mu_s s_i e^{-\beta \left(\frac{(p_i - qA)^2}{2m} - \mu_s \cdot s_i \cdot B - \mu \right)}}{\prod_i \left(1 + e^{-\beta \left(\frac{(p_i - qA)^2}{2m} - \mu_s \cdot s_i \cdot B - \mu \right)} \right)} \quad (11)$$

Therefore by differentiating the grand potential with respect to the magnetic field B , we obtain the magnetization M as:

$$M = -\left(\frac{\partial \Omega}{\partial B} \right)_{T, \mu} \quad (12)$$

The external magnetic field influences the energy levels of particles with magnetic moments, such as electrons. In the presence of a magnetic field, the energy levels of these particles split due to the Zeeman Effect. This splitting leads to a change in the population of energy levels, which can affect properties like the system magnetic moment and magnetization. From Eq. (12) magnetization in a grand canonical ensemble is the negative partial derivative of the grand canonical ensemble Ω with respect to the magnetic field B at constant temperature T and chemical potential μ . The grand potential Ω is related to the grand partition function Z which is given by Eq. (7). From the previously derived formula the grand partition function in the presence of magnetic field is given in Eq. (6). Taking the natural logarithm of Eq. (6)

$$\ln Z = \sum_i \ln \left(1 + e^{-\beta \left(\frac{(p_i - qA)^2}{2m} - \mu_s \cdot s_i \cdot B - \mu \right)} \right) \quad (13)$$

Thus, the grand potential Ω becomes

$$\Omega = -k_B T \sum_i \ln \left(1 + e^{-\beta \left(\frac{(p_i - qA)^2}{2m} - \mu_s \cdot s_i \cdot B - \mu \right)} \right) \quad (14)$$

To find the magnetization M , we need to take the derivative of Ω with respect to B which is given in Eq. (12). Substitute Ω into Eq. (12)

$$M = k_B T \sum_i \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial B} \ln \left(1 + e^{-\beta \left(\frac{(p_i - qA)^2}{2m} - \mu_s \cdot s_i \cdot B - \mu \right)} \right) \right) \quad (15)$$

Applying chain rule to the logarithm

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial B} \ln \left(1 + e^{-\beta \left(\frac{(p_i - qA)^2}{2m} - \mu_s \cdot s_i \cdot B - \mu \right)} \right) \quad (16)$$

$$= \frac{1}{1 + e^{-\beta \left(\frac{(p_i - qA)^2}{2m} - \mu_s \cdot s_i \cdot B - \mu \right)}} \cdot (-\beta \mu_s s_i) e^{-\beta \left(\frac{(p_i - qA)^2}{2m} - \mu_s \cdot s_i \cdot B - \mu \right)}$$

Simplifying the expression inside the sum

$$M = k_B T \sum_i \left(\frac{-\beta \mu_s s_i e^{-\beta \left(\frac{(p_i - qA)^2}{2m} - \mu_s \cdot s_i \cdot B - \mu \right)}}{1 + e^{-\beta \left(\frac{(p_i - qA)^2}{2m} - \mu_s \cdot s_i \cdot B - \mu \right)}} \right) \quad (17)$$

Simplifying Eq. (17)

$$M = -\beta k_B T \sum_i \mu_s s_i \frac{e^{-\beta \left(\frac{(p_i - qA)^2}{2m} - \mu_s \cdot s_i \cdot B - \mu \right)}}{1 + e^{-\beta \left(\frac{(p_i - qA)^2}{2m} - \mu_s \cdot s_i \cdot B - \mu \right)}} \quad (18)$$

The fraction in Eq. (18) is the Fermi Dirac distribution function $f(\varepsilon)$ which is given by [8].

$$f(\varepsilon) = \frac{1}{e^{\beta(\varepsilon - \mu)} + 1} \quad (19)$$

Thus

$$M = - \sum_i \mu_s \cdot s_i \cdot f(\varepsilon) \quad (20)$$

Magnetic susceptibility χ describes how the magnetization M changes with the magnetic field B [6].

$$\chi = \left(\frac{\partial M}{\partial B} \right)_{T, \mu} \quad (21)$$

Taking the derivative Of M with respect to B :

$$\chi = - \sum_i \mu_s s_i \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial B} f(\varepsilon) \right) \quad (22)$$

Using the chain rule for the Fermi Dirac distribution:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial B} f(\varepsilon) = (-\beta \mu_s s_i) e^{\beta(\varepsilon - \mu)} \left(\frac{1}{(e^{\beta(\varepsilon - \mu)} + 1)^2} \right) \quad (23)$$

Substituting Eq. (23) back into the expression for χ :

$$\chi = \beta \sum_i \mu_s^2 s_i^2 \frac{e^{\beta(\varepsilon - \mu)}}{(1 + e^{\beta(\varepsilon - \mu)})^2} \quad (24)$$

The factor $\beta = 1/k_B T$ describes the rate of change $f(\varepsilon)$ with respect to energy becomes sharper as the temperature decreases since β increases with T . The magnetic moment μ_s is given by $-g\mu_B$ where g is the g factor and μ_B is the bohr magneton given by $\frac{e\hbar}{2m}$ and the spin is given by $\hbar\sigma/2$. The susceptibility can thus be written as:

$$\chi = \frac{1}{k_B T} \sum_i \left(-g \frac{e\hbar}{2m}\right)_i^2 \cdot \left(\frac{\hbar\sigma}{2}\right)_i^2 \cdot f(\varepsilon) \quad (25)$$

Simplifying this equation, we have

$$\chi = \frac{1}{k_B T} \sum_i -g^2 \frac{e^2 \hbar^2}{4m^2} \cdot \frac{\hbar^2 \sigma^2}{4} \cdot f(\varepsilon) \quad (26)$$

Therefore the final equation is given as

$$\chi = -g^2 \frac{e^2 \hbar^4 \sigma^2}{16m^2 k_B T} \sum_i f(\varepsilon) \quad (27)$$

The magnetic susceptibility equation in Eq. (27) describes a measure of how a particle will be magnetized in an applied magnetic field in a grand canonical ensemble. Eq. (27) is an intrinsic property of the material and depends on the quantum states of the particles within it. Eq. (27) also indicates that susceptibility depends inversely on temperature. Higher temperature generally leads to lower susceptibility and vice versa. Since Eq. (27) incorporates the Fermi Dirac distribution, it accounts for the quantum statistical nature of particles, particularly electrons in solid. This is important for physics of low temperature where quantum effects become significant. In the grand canonical ensemble, Eq. (27) reflects the balance between thermal fluctuations, quantum statistical effects and the contribution of individual magnetic moments and spin to the overall magnetization.

4. Conclusion

Magnetism can have a significant effect on the behavior of a grand canonical ensemble, as it can influence the alignment of the particle magnetic moments and their energy levels; this is an important consideration in the study of magnetic systems and their behavior in different ensemble. In this work we have derived an expression for a modified partition function in the presence of an applied magnetic field, the magnetization and the magnetic susceptibility for a particle in a grand canonical ensemble.

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